
HOW-TO GUIDE:

ETHICS CAFE

INTRODUCTION

The *Ethics Café* offers a unique format within any conference, inspired by the conversational spirit of Viennese coffee houses. Participants are encouraged to bring their coffee and immerse themselves in the kind of engaging, informal discussions characteristic of these classic settings. The *Ethics Café* is a dynamic, interactive format designed to foster open dialogue, reflection, and shared learning on ethical issues broadly, as well as focusing on a specific topic chosen for the session.

Below are the key components and steps to organize and run a successful *Ethics Café*.

KEY PRINCIPLES

One Inspiring Speaker

- Choose a speaker who can provide thought-provoking insights on a specific ethical topic.
- The talk should be brief, slide-free, and focused on inspiring further discussion rather than delivering a formal lecture.

Audience Engagement

- Create opportunities for audience members to easily share their thoughts and questions.
- Provide accessible microphones or other methods for audience interaction.

Facilitative, Not Dominant Conveners

- The conveners (session chairs) should maintain a supportive, low-key role—stepping in only to reenergize the discussion or provide new prompts if the conversation stalls.

Eye-to-Eye Dialogue

- Avoid the traditional podium setup. Instead, position the speaker in the centre of the group to foster a conversational and personal atmosphere.
- Passing microphones from participant to participant can be time-consuming and often leads to a traditional Q&A format, which should be avoided to maintain the conversational, interactive nature of the *Ethics Café*.

FORMAT OPTIONS

In-Person Sessions

Role of the Speaker: The talk can be provocative or humorous, provided it sparks thought and encourages dialogue among participants. The talk shouldn't lead to a traditional Q&A between the audience and the speaker. Ideally, after the introductory remarks or presentation, the speaker shifts into a more participatory role.

Seating Arrangement: Use the “cinnamon roll” seating style—arrange chairs in a spiral with 2-3 open pathways leading toward the centre. This creates a space that allows for eye-to-eye exchanges and ensures that participants have easy access to microphones while creating an intimate, engaging environment. An alternative seating arrangement is the “catwalk” style, which promotes better engagement and interaction. Traditional theatre-style seating should be avoided unless it's a 360-degree setup.

Space in the Centre: The speaker must stand in the centre of the group (approx. 1m²), with a handheld microphone to ensure they can connect with participants without being isolated on a stage.

Role of Conveners: After a brief introduction to the topic, format and speaker bio, stay in the background, only stepping in to moderate if the discussion becomes stagnant or needs new input.

Image 1: Dialogue at the EBW 2019. Standing microphone. Those not speaking are sitting down. Those who want to add to the conversation queue behind two microphones opposite each other.

Virtual Sessions

Dialogue Structure: The virtual format calls for a distinctive structure to maintain engagement and foster audience participation. The convener and speaker will engage in a dialogue on the speaker's topic (approximately 10 minutes). They should align beforehand on key topics and talking points for the *Ethics Café – virtual edition*. The conversation should follow a dialogue style, with the conveners' posing questions and sharing reflections based on the speaker's insights. This approach facilitates easy listening, encourages audience members to ask questions via chat, and fosters an intimate, interactive atmosphere.

Podcast Arrangement: The dialogue is conducted in the virtual space as a live podcast. Using a video of the presenters can be distracting. We also recommend avoiding the use of slide decks to allow participants to fully engage with the conversation. If desired, a maximum of three slides can be used to signal topic transitions. Consider using cartoons or images to maintain visual interest and support the discussion. Using a video of the speaker and convener having a conversation can be distracting or may come across as monotonous.

Role of the Speaker: The talk can be provocative or humorous, provided it sparks thought and encourages dialogue among participants online and a conversation with the convener without presentation slides. The talk shouldn't lead to a traditional Q&A between the audience and the speaker. Ideally, after the introductory remarks or presentation, the speaker shifts into a more participatory role.

Role of Conveners: After a brief introduction to the topic, format and speaker bio, conveners actively moderate and enter in a dialogue with the speaker. It may be worth considering a division of roles between moderating the chat and facilitating the dialogue among conveners.

Audience Participation: Audience participation takes place through a shared chat visible to all participants, allowing them to post comments, thoughts, or questions. Other participants can respond to these contributions, fostering interaction and engagement among attendees. One convener's role is to filter and select some of these comments or questions to incorporate into the dialogue with the speaker. The convener may choose whether the chat is visible to the speaker, only to themselves, or managed by a moderator who highlights and shares preselected items with the convener.

“Actually, we’re only taking tissue samples.”

Image 2: Cartoon used as one of three slides presented at the Ethics Café - virtual edition EBW 2020

DURATION

The *Ethics Café* should have the same duration as a standard session at the conference to maintain consistency and focus (approx. 1 ½ hours), thereof 10-minute talk by the speaker.

TIMING TIP

The early morning slot following a conference dinner is ideal. While it may seem unconventional at first, feedback suggests that it creates the perfect environment: engaged participants who are energized by thoughtful conversation or a relaxed, easy-to-follow format for those who may be recovering from the previous night's events.

BONUS TIPS

Location, Location, Location: Careful consideration should be given to the placement of standing microphones (we recommend using two). Consistent microphone positions encourage participants to contribute from the same locations, fostering focused discussion and mutual engagement. Properly positioned microphones, along with thoughtfully arranged seating, are essential to creating a comfortable and effective environment that supports meaningful dialogue.

Record and Share: Always consider recording the session and publishing it as a podcast (with participant consent). This extends the *Ethics Café* dialogue beyond the conference and allows attendees and others to revisit the insights shared.

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This guide was authored by [Dr. Michaela Th. Mayrhofer](#), who has, over the years, organized the Ethics Café as a staple feature at both the Hands-On and Europe Biobank Week (EBW) congress. On behalf of all conveners, we extend our gratitude to the speakers and participants—past and future—for contributing to the event's success and making it their own.

CONTACT: elsi-helpdesk@bbmri-eric.eu

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